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CLINICAL EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF LEECHING IN KNEE OSTEOARTHRITIS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Leeching Therapy (Irsal-e-Alaq) is an integral part of regimental therapy used in Unani System of Medicine. It has been successfully practiced by Greeko-Arabic physicians in the management of Joint disorders since antiquity. Osteoarthritis is the commonest form of arthritis and is a major cause of pain and disability in the elderly. The incidence of arthritis has increased considerably in present scenario. Objective: The present study was aimed to evaluate the efficacy and safety of Leeching Therapy (Irsal-e-Alaq) in the patients of knee Osteoarthritis on scientific parameters. Methodology: The study was conducted in the Regimental Therapy ward RRIUM, Srinagar. 75 patients of OA were enrolled in the trial after obtaining their informed consents. All the patients were clinically assessed and diagnosed on the basis of thorough history, clinical and radiological examination of the affected joint. Then 2 fresh leeches were applied on the affected areas of the beard till leeches were belly filled and fell down of their own (approximately 45 minutes). Then antiseptic dressing was applied on the site. This leech therapy was done every after 15 days for two months. The efficacy of Leeching therapy was assessed on the basis of Western Ontario and McMaster University (WOMAC) Score and Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) Score. Results: The results were analyzed statistically by using a Paired Student's t-test. There was a significant reduction in the WOMAC and VAS scores of post-treatment group (P <0.01) as compared to pre-treatment group. Conclusion: It is concluded in this observational non comparison study that Leeching therapy may be used safely and effectively in the management of Osteoarthritis.

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INTRODUCTION

In Unani System of Medicine, all joint disorders are mentioned under the heading of *Wajaulmafasil*. *Tahajuremafasil* (*Wajaur-Rukba*) is that form of *Wajaul mafasil* in which the joints become stiff and movement are harshly limited. It is caused by unusual viscid material that squeezes into the joint space to get solidified. It is typically involves elderly persons and is associated with pain^{1,2}. *Tahajuremafasil* can be clinically linked with Osteoarthritis (OA). OA is a major cause of morbidity, physical limitation and increased health care utilization³. According to the World Health Organization, OA is the second most common musculoskeletal condition (30 %) after back pain (50 %). The reported prevalence of OA from a study in rural India is 5.78 %⁴. A recent WHO report on the worldwideweight of disease indicates that knee OA alone is probably to become the fourth most important reason of disability in women and the eighth most important in men. Knee OA is more common in Asians and Afro-Caribbeans. With the increase in population of the elderly people it has become the major health problem nowadays⁵. As it has no make well, the important objective of treatment is to relieve pain and stiffness and maintain and improve physical function⁶. In Unani system of medicine, leech therapy(*Irsal-e-alaq*) has been mentioned for the treatment of joint pain⁷.

Irsale Alaq (Leech or Hirudo therapy) is a method of blood-letting which involves the withdrawal of blood in a considerable quantity from the body with the help of Leeches.⁸ It is actually a blood sucking process with the help of medicinal leeches for prevention and treatment of various diseases. The therapeutic application of this therapy is known from the time of extreme antiquity and is still alive in present health scenario. Leeching (Hirudotherapy) is one of the most important and widely practiced method of regimental therapy used since long⁹. Modern study of leech therapy has also shown significant results in many diseases. Surgeons uses the leech therapy in plastic and reconstructive surgery and for the treatment of postoperative venous congestion and graftrejections¹⁰. Leeches contain more than 100 pharmacologically and biologically active enzymes having different actions like analgesic, vasodilatation, anti thrombotic action.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present study was conducted at Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine, Srinagar, Ministry of AYUSH, Govt. of India. 50 Patients suffering from osteoarthritis, of both sex and between the age of 40 to 80 years were included in this study. Their written consents were taken. Before starting the therapy, the routine pathological, biochemical and radiological investigations including BT and CT were performed to exclude any bleeding disorder. Fresh leeches were procured and were then identified by zoologist. Then under aseptic procedures, 2 fresh leeches were applied on the affected areas of the beard till leeches were belly filled and fell down of there own (approximately 45 minutes). Then antiseptic dressing was applied on the site. This leech therapy was done every after 15 days for two months.

Parameters of the Study (1) Pain (2) Swelling (3) Morning stiffness (4) Tenderness (S) Decreased range of Movement 0-3 score was given as per the severity of parameter (0 for absent/normal and 3 for severest form of parameter)The parameters were observed before the treatment (Baseline) and at the end of 1st week (1st FU), 2nd week (IIndFU). One week after the completion of treatment, a follow-up (IIIrd FU) was done to note any changes in the parameters after the stoppage of treatment. Before treatment and after treatment score was compared and analysed by paired 't' test.

RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of Patients according to age.

Age in Years	No. of Patients	% of Patients
35-45	3	5
46-55	15	25
56-65	36	60
66-75	06	10
Total	60	100

Table 2: Distribution of Patients according to Sex.

Male	Female	Total
25	35	60

Table 3: Distribution of Patients according to Affected Joint.

Name of Joint	No. Of patients	% of Patients
Right Knee	10	16
Left Knee	14	23
Both	36	60

Table 4: Distribution of Patients according to Sign and Symptoms.

Sign and Symptoms	No. of patients
Pain	52
Tenderness	34
stiffness	34
Restricted movement	60
Swelling	48

Table 5: Effect of Leeching Therapy on WOMAC scores.

Symptoms	Before Treatment	After Treatment
Pain	33.4	15.4
Stiffness	24.5	10.1
Daily Activity	51.3	20.2

Table 6: Effect of Leeching Therapy on VAS scores.

Symptoms	Before Treatment	After Treatment
Pain	10	5
Stiffness	09	2
Swelling	13	5
tenderness	20	9
Restricted movement	26	6

Out of 75 patients enrolled, 15 were lost to follow-up and were excluded from the study, leaving behind 60 patients who completed the study. Out of 60 patients 35 (63.33%) were females and 25 (36.67%) patients were males. The Mean $\pm$ SD of age was 54 years. The highest incidence (60%) was observed in the age group of 56-65 years while the least incidence (5%) was seen in the age group of 35-45 years. 36 (60%) patients had bilateral OA, while 10 (16.67%) patients complained of right-sided and 14 (23.335%) patients complained of left-sided OA. Regarding clinical features, only 34 patients complained of tenderness, 60 had restricted movements, 34 had stiffness, 48 had swelling and all 52 patients complained of pain as shown in table no. 1 to 4

Effect of Leeching Therapy on WOMAC score

WOMAC Scale is an internationally accepted scale which consists of questions based on three symptoms viz., pain, stiffness and difficulty in performing physical activities. WOMAC scores were compared and statistically analyzed by applying paired Student's t-test in all patients before and after treatment. The mean WOMAC scores of post treatment groups were found to be significantly lowered ($P < 0.001$) when compared with mean WOMAC scores of pre treatment group. [Table 5].

Effect of Leeching Therapy on VAS score

VAS scores were compared and statistically analyzed in all the patients before and after treatment. The mean VAS scores of post-treatment groups were found to be significantly lowered ($P < 0.001$) when compared with mean VAS scores of pre-treatment group. [Table 6].

DISCUSSION

Leeching is a type of regimental therapy used to relieve pain and swelling in OA. In present study, leeching produced significant improvement on various symptoms and signs including pain, tenderness, stiffness, swelling, WOMAC and VAS Scores. But there was no effect on the degenerative changes of joints as observed in the Xrays of pre and post-treatment groups. Besides, the therapy was found to be safe and well tolerated as no adverse effects were noticed during and after the treatment and overall compliance to the therapy was good.

CONCLUSION

It may be concluded that the leeching therapy is an effective and safe regimen in the symptomatic management of management of knee OA. Thus further studies of long duration and long follow-up period with randomized standard controlled designs on large population need to be carried out for further exploration of efficacy and safety of leeching therapy.

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